

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

Policy Brief n° 3

Learnings from 12 Living Labs

Mette Vaarst (Aarhus University), Bernadette Oehen (FiBL), Annick Spaans (ZLTO), Florence Bonnet-Beaugrand (INRAE)

This contributes to the objective of identifying levers/incentives for adherence to prudent use principles by veterinarians and farmers and of developing integrative, participative and innovative approaches for animal health.

The European Union is the world's second largest pork producer and one of the world's largest poultry meat producers. EU is also a major producer of beef and veal with a total herd of around 78 million cattle and a substantial producer of milk and milk products with a total milk production around 155 million tonnes per year.

This policy brief should particularly relevant for stakeholders and animal health professionals, as well as researchers and policy-makers interested in social innovation, from any European country.

CONTEXT

A part of the ROADMAP project has been the work in Living Labs, where sector actors together worked at different levels to reduce antimicrobial use (AMU). Initiatives such as Living Labs had not existed in any participating countries before concerning animal health, disease and AMU. Early analyses of the sectors and backgrounds for initiating Living Labs pointed to huge and interesting differences between countries. The learning and co-learning involved the whole process from initiating the Living Labs, to taking decisions on their potential continuation or finalisation.

Participatory research methodologies, action research and multi-actor involvement as applied in the Living Labs in ROADMAP were discussed to build on participation with a negotiated and mutually agreed aim of reaching a common goal on reduced AMU. ROADMAP partners co-developed 12 Living Labs and other participatory approaches, adjusted to national and local contexts and focusing on different animal species and sectors. The different Living Labs developed multiple versions of the 'optimal mix of stakeholders', which were relevant according to the diverse contexts within the project. In particular, farmers and farm-related actors and much of the veterinary, agricultural and food industry were core to the changes regarding the prudent use of antimicrobials. This differs from the usual Living Labs, where stakeholders and end-users are citizen-oriented.

RELATED PROJECT PUBLICATIONS

Vaerst M., Bonnet-Beaugrand F., Oehen B., Prinsen H., Spaans A. 2021. [Identifying levers to transition to prudent antimicrobial use through multi-stakeholder Living Labs](#). In, 72. *Annual Meeting of the European Federation of Animal Science (EAAP)*, Davos, Suisse, 2021/08/30-2021/09/03, 465.

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The ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 817626.

RESULTS

Living Labs as a capacity building tool

The Living Labs brought stakeholders together and aimed to create mutual understanding and trust, which impact institutions and practices at a more overall level in many respects, regarding the common project goal of reducing AMU significantly.

The Living Labs in itself has been an achievement, even if long-term outcomes are difficult to measure. Negotiation and learning have been paramount.

Wise and sound facilitation of the meetings was a crucial point in the adherence of stakeholders.

However, it is very time-consuming. LLs need time to build trustful partnerships and maintain the working relationship.

Systemic Challenges and lock-ins in the livestock sector

The Living Lab co-learning events pointed out the lock-ins in the value chain, especially in integrated livestock sectors or sectors implying animal mixing and transportation.

Preventive practices have been the main focus at the farm and advice level.

However, steering and monitoring indicators sets have been debated but no real-time monitoring tool could emerge, due to the different timelines of stakeholders.

AMU has been considered a non-priority compared to the economic situation, biodiversity, energy, or environmental issues.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Make funding available for participation in agri-living labs

Include Living Labs in the vocational education funding

Foster research on living labs evaluation indicators aimed at social innovations and organisational dynamic capabilities building

Provide support for the education of facilitators and their professional recognition.

Make funding available for the logistics of living labs so that the scientists may focus on research.

Focus on systemic and governance solutions to foster livestock sectors changes.

Foster coaching and pair groups intervention schemes.

Focus specific calls on public and private technical research and innovation on real-time health and AMU monitoring.

Raise awareness about the links between biodiversity, environmental issues and AMU.

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